

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY ON THE INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF CFRTP IN MICRO-DROPLET TEST

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ABSTRACT

In the light-weight design of automobile structures, specific strength and toughness should be considered as essential properties. However, they strongly depend on the interfacial property between fiber and matrix. Additionally, in the case of automotive application, operating temperature of CFRTP must be considered. To evaluate temperature dependence on the interfacial property of CFRTP, micro-mechanical tests were carried out. Carbon fiber as reinforcement and polypropylene as polymer matrix were used in this study. In a micro-mechanical test, influence of the temperature on the interfacial shear strength was studied by micro-droplet test from 25 to 100 degree Celsius. Finite element analysis (FEA) of micro-droplet test was conducted with three-dimensional finite elements model. Stress distribution in matrix were obtained by FEA. From result of experiment, interfacial property of CF and PP showed temperature dependency with perfect de-bonding surface. From FEA, stress distribution in matrix was obtained. Initial failure of matrix at end of shape was occurred even under room temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) is being investigated for general industrial materials, such as in automobiles industry. According to relatively high mechanical properties and low density, CFRP has been expected as desirable materials for light-weight structure. However, due to the low productivity and relatively high cost, CFRP has not been widely applied in mass-production. In order to solve this issue, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) with affordable resins, has been developed to achieve excellent formability and mechanical properties [1].

In the light-weight design of automobile structures, specific strength and toughness should be considered as essential properties. However, they strongly depend on the interfacial property between fiber and matrix. Additionally, in the case of automotive application, operating temperature of CFRTP must be considered. Because polymers for CFRTP show viscoelastic behavior, the mechanical properties will be influenced by operating temperature. This variation in mechanical properties of polymer properly affects radial stress on fiber surface, which is essential parameter for interfacial property. Thus, it is necessary to make clear influence of temperature on the interfacial property of CFRTP.

Typically, interfacial property can be assessed by employing single fiber composite model such as single fiber fragmentation, micro-bond, pull-out, and push-out tests [2]. However, the result from fragmentation test is restricted by the characteristics of polymer such as failure strain or residual stress. Furthermore, variation in fiber strength significantly affects the result of fragmentation test. Both of the pull-out and push-out test should be promised that the filament perfectly placed on the load direction. Therefore, among above-mentioned methods, micro-droplet test is one of the most effective approach to evaluate shear failure of fiber/ matrix interface by simple pull-out of fiber from micro-scale polymer droplet. This test follows pulling fiber out of matrix through knife-edge and completes de-bonding at fiber/matrix interface. Consequently, the interfacial property is derived by the reaction force during the pull-out. This method can acquire several data in one specimen, because the fiber pull out can be completed without fiber break. Additionally, this test can be performed at variable temperatures by combining with a thermal chamber [3, 4]. However, at relatively high temperature

such as stress-free temperature of polymer, matrix fracture can occur simultaneously with de-bonding. And that will negatively affect on evaluating precise interfacial properties. Hence, numerical simulation for micro-droplet test is necessary to provide stress distribution in polymer matrix. For numerical simulation, The approximate two-dimensional finite element model (FEM) in past with elliptical shape, cylinder shape or circular shape were proposed [2, 5-7]. However, approaches of three-dimensional FEM with meniscus shape were scarce, and two-dimensional FEM with meniscus shape was also few [8, 9].

In this study, the interfacial property between carbon fiber (CF) and thermoplastics was investigated by experimental and numerical method. Polypropylene (PP) were used as polymer matrix. In order to improve interfacial properties between CF and PP, maleic acid modified polypropylene (MAPP) was fabricated by combining kneaded homo polypropylene (Home-PP) and maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene (MA-g-PP). Influence of the temperature on the interfacial shear strength was studied by micro-droplet test from 25 to 100 degree Celsius. Finite element analysis (FEA) of micro-droplet test was conducted with three-dimensional FEM. Stress distribution in matrix were obtained by FEA. In addition, residue of polymer matrix on de-bonding surface of CF and geometry of droplet were obtained by both optical observation and scanning electron microscope (SEM).

2 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

2.1 Materials

CF as reinforcement was manufactured by Toray Industries, Inc., and grade is T700S. In preparation of CF specimens, sizing agent on surface of fiber removed by acetone. Because, sizing agent on surface of fiber disturbs attachment of CF and polymer. CFs were soaking in acetone base for 4 hours, after that CFs were washed by distilled water. This procedure was repeated 3 times. And CFs were dried in the vacuum dryer at 90 degrees Celsius for 12 hours.

PP was used as matrix in this study. In case of PP, it is known well that PP has low interfacial property with CF. Since, in order to improve interfacial properties between CF and PP, MAPP was fabricated by combining kneaded Homo-PP and MA-g-PP with an extruder (Labo Plastomill 10C100S90, Toyo Seiki, Japan). Homo-PP (Y6005GM, MFR=60g/10min at 230 degrees Celsius/2.16 kg) was produced by Prime Polymer Co. MA-g-PP (Yumex 1010) was produced by Sanyo Chemical Industries. The maleic-acid content in the MA-g-PP was 10 wt%. Table 1 shows the kneading conditions.

Table 1: The kneading conditions of MAPP.

	Time [min]	Temperature [°C]	Rotation rate [rpm]
Conditions	15	185	30

2.2 Micro-droplet test

Micro-mechanical tests are important for evaluation of adhesion between reinforcement and matrix. To evaluate influence of the temperature on the interfacial shear strength, micro-droplet test was conducted. In preparation of micro-droplet specimen as shown in Figure 1, the alumina plate was selected as holder. CF was stuck on alumina by epoxy resin. Then polymer and alumina holder were heated up until the resin melting and used support to stick polymer on CF surface in 10 minutes. For test, the specimen was loaded between two knife-edge jigs. At that time, the length (L) of embedded CF was measured by two-dimensional measurement software (AR-U120P3MF, ARTRAY Co., Ltd., Japan). Interfacial shear strength was measured during a unidirectional pulling process at a speed of 0.12 mm/minutes. The testing temperature from 25 to 100 degree Celsius were controlled by thermo-chamber (Figure 2). Interfacial shears strength was calculated using the following equation:

$$\tau = \frac{F}{\pi DL} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Schematic of preparation for micro-droplet test specimens (left) and test (right).

Figure 2: micro-droplet test equipment with thermal chamber.

2.3 Result and discussions

Results of micro-droplet test under different temperatures are showed in Figure 3. From the scatter plot of interfacial shear strength and embedded length, interfacial strength appeared to depend on embedded length. Figure 4 shows comparison of interfacial shear strength in different temperature. Interfacial shear strength declined with temperature increasing. Interfacial shear strength is established by chemical bond and radial stress on fiber surface. Chemical bond depends on functional group on CF and PP and unrelated to temperature. Radial stress on fiber surface depends mechanical properties of polymer. According to viscoelastic of polymer, mechanical properties of PP has temperature dependency and it decreased with temperature increasing. Since those characteristics probably release radial stress on fiber surface and interfacial shear strength appeared temperature dependency.

Result of observation by SEM are showed in Figure 5. The de-bonding surface of specimens showed clear surface. It was hard to detect residual resin on the de-bonding surface. Since the perfect de-bonding has occurred in each temperature. However, in Figure 5 (d), the fracture of polymer was occurred. The matrix resin became soften due to high temperature, and it was easy to occur biting of jig on matrix. Since the embedded length used for calculation was longer than actual de-bonding length. And the interfacial shear strength represented lower value compare to precise value.

Figure 3: Results of micro-droplet test under different temperatures: (a) 25 °C, (b) 50 °C, (c) 75 °C, (d) 100 °C.

Figure 4: Comparison of interfacial shear strength under different temperatures.

Figure 5: SEM observation of de-bonding surface: (a) 25 °C, (b) 50 °C, (c) 75 °C, (d) 100 °C.

3 NUMERICAL STUDY

In this section, according to numerical simulation, modeling method, parameter study and finite element analysis were discussed.

3.1 Geometry of micro-droplet

The profile of droplet on fiber has been proposed approximate FEM in past with elliptical shape, cylinder shape or circular shape [2, 5-7]. However, droplet is deposited on fiber by surface tension. And end of liquid polymer form a meniscus, which remain upon polymer curing. The profile include meniscus were approached according to Carroll theory [8-10]. From their result, the profile was showed good agreement to actual specimen. Hence, in this study, determination of profile was achieved by Carroll theory.

Provided that the fiber diameter is small enough, it assume that the effects of gravity are negligible and the fiber is cylindrical, the profile can be described by following equation:

$$y^2 = h^2(1 - k^2 \sin^2 \psi) \quad (2)$$

$$x = \pm[arF(\psi, k) + hE(\psi, k)] \quad (3)$$

where

$$a = \frac{h \cos \theta - r}{h - \cos \theta} \quad (4)$$

$$k^2 = \frac{h^2 - a^2 r^2}{h^2} \quad (5)$$

and where h , r and θ are the maximum droplet height, fiber radius and contact angle of droplet on fiber (Figure 6). The variable ψ is the angle between a point on profile and y-axis and varies from 0 to ψ_{max} . F and E are the Legendre's standard incomplete integrals of the first and second as a function of auxiliary variable ψ and parameter k . Since, the coordinates of these point are $(x, y) = (\pm l/2, r)$, as following equation derived from (2) and (3):

$$r^2 = h^2(1 - k^2 \sin^2 \psi_{max}) \quad (6)$$

$$l = \pm [arF(\psi_{\max}, k) + hE(\psi_{\max}, k)] \quad (7)$$

from equation (6) and (7), unknown parameters (ψ_{\max}) would be determined, and the embedded length, maximum droplet radius and contact angle were obtained from experiment with microscope observation. The profile of droplet was achieved through equation (1) and (2). From the experimental result, the contact angle present 26 degree with 3.59 standard deviation. For embedded length, it selected as 100 μm . About selection of embedded length, it would be discussed in next section.

Figure 6: The various parameters in micro-droplet test.

3.2 Finite element model

Stress distribution in matrix were estimated using finite element program ABAQUS/Standard 6.14-5. The profile defined in Section 3.1 was incorporated into FEM along with carbon fiber. The geometry of all part were drawn in Fusion 360. Then the date of geometry incorporated into HyperMesh, in order to create meshes in each components. Figure 7 shows the axis-symmetric three-dimensional FEM. In determination of the embedded length, the droplet is small, the meniscus shape probably become significant due to its non-negligible size compared with the small droplet diameter. However, in case of large embedded length providing large droplet lessens the significance of meniscus shape [7]. Therefore, 35640 solid elements for matrix has embedded length of 100 μm and the 10800 solid elements consisted the fiber which has radius of 3.5 μm and shown in Table 2. The jig with 45 degree knife-edge and load-cell which used to determine reaction force as rigid body input into model. Table 3 present the input date for calculation. In the model, the matrix is represented as J_2 flow elastic-plastic material. For the fiber, because of higher modulus and strength, fiber will not change these shape obviously and complete test without break. Since fiber is assumed as elastic isotropic material.

To simulate the de-bonding process during the fiber pullout, the contact surface of fiber and matrix tied by node to node as initial contact. And then the interfacial fracture was controlled by critical energy criterion. To determine critical energy criterion, the energy-based criterion theory which proposed by Scheer and Narin was used as following equation:

$$F_d = F_d(l, G_c, \Delta T) \quad (8)$$

where, G_c is the critical energy release rate, ΔT is cape of experiment and stress-free temperate. According to the energy-based criterion theory, to determine G_c function be proposed three type and results showed small difference [11]. In this study, simple analyses function was used to calculate critical energy criterion and the function was showed as following:

$$F_d = \pi r_1^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{2G_{ic}}{r_1 C_{33s}} - \frac{D_{3s} \Delta T}{C_{33s}}} \right) \quad (9)$$

where

$$C_{33s} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{V_1}{V_2 E_m} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$D_{3s} = \frac{1}{2} (\alpha_A - \alpha_m) \quad (11)$$

$$V_1 = 1.5 \left(\frac{r_1}{r_2} \right)^2, V_2 = 1 - V_1 \quad (12)$$

r_1 and r_2 are radius of fiber and matrix, G_{ic} is critical energy criterion, E_A is Axial modulus of fiber, E_m is modulus of matrix, α_A and α_m are thermal expanding coefficient of fiber and matrix. V_1 and V_2 are volume fraction of fiber and matrix. Above those parameters, unknown parameter is r_2 . In order to decide r_2 , microscope observation was carried out and results were shown in Figure 8. The results presented that maximum height of droplet has linear relationship with embedded length. Therefore, r_2 can be decided from plot of maximum height of droplet and embedded length. Figure 9 showed results of micro-droplet fitting by simple analyses function which approached by Scheer and Narin. From the result, the critical energy criterion has value of 250 J/m². Since the value of 250 J/m² as critical energy criterion was incorporated into FEA.

Figure 7: The axis-symmetric three-dimensional FE model.

Table 2: Number of element for FEM.

	Fiber	Matrix
Elements	10800	35640

Table 3: Material properties used in FEA.

	Fiber
Diameter [μm]	7
Density [g/cm^3]	1.8
Axial modulus [GPa]	230
Axial Poisson's ratio	0.2
Axial thermal expanding coefficient [m/K]	-0.4×10^{-6}
	Matrix
Density [g/cm^3]	0.9
Modulus [MPa]	1600
Poisson's ratio	0.4
Yield stress [MPa]	50.7
Thermal expanding coefficient [m/K]	4×10^{-5}

Figure 8: Relationship between embedded length and maximum height of droplet.

Figure 9: Graph fitting for experiment.

3.4 Result and discussion

Figure 10 shows stress distribution in matrix under each time with room temperature. The edge of jig was contacted matrix at 0.747 s passed, at that time, the end of meniscus shape showed stress concentration and the stress in matrix reached yield stress of polymer as shown in Figure 10 (a). Figure 10 (b) and (c) show procedure of initial crack occurrence at the end of meniscus shape. When the time passed to 1.843 s, matrix occurred initial crack under edge of jig. And then the crack progressed towards interface direction with pull-out process, since failure of matrix under edge of jig was occurred at 1.975 s. After initial failure, the stress concentration were occurred in both of surface contact. One is surface contact of jig and matrix, another is interface contact as shown in Figure 10 (d). Through FEA, the stress distribution in matrix were obtained at initial part of experiment, and the initial failure of matrix also was obtained in FEM even under room temperature. Since, it probably lead the embedded length to be shorter. Therefore, it is necessary to more carefully evaluate the result of experiment, especially at high temperature. Additionally, it is necessary to clarify the effect of edge positioning on embedded length.

Figure 10: Stress distribution in matrix at each time: (a) 0.747 s, (b) 1.843 s, (c) 1.975 s, (d) 3.580 s.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, the interfacial property between CF and thermoplastics was investigated by experimental and numerical method. In experimental study, micro-droplet test was carried out. Interfacial shear strength declined with temperature increasing and result of SEM showed perfect debonding in each temperature. Above experimental result, it can be concluded that interfacial property between CF and MAPP showed temperature dependency. According to FEA, stress distribution in matrix was obtained. Initial failure of matrix was occurred at initial stage of experiment even in room temperature. Since it is necessary to clarify the effect of edge positioning on embedded length. And influence of operating temperature in FEA are under investigated.

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